

1 Endothelin receptors EDNRA and EDNRB are active during TE specification.

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe activation of endothelial
8 receptors EDNRA and EDNRB during TE specification in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

9 Citations

10 1. Square, T.A., Jandzik, D., Massey, J.L., Romášek, M., Stein, H.P., Hansen, A.W., Purkayastha, A.,
11 Cattell, M.V. and Medeiros, D.M., 2020. Evolution of the endothelin pathway drove neural crest cell
12 diversification. *Nature*, 585(7826), pp.563-568.